

RESOURCES

NEW RESOURCES: 11 SEPTEMBER, 2001

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Web Sources

A web search on 11 September 2001, using the google search engine will turn up at least 5.5 million hits. Below I have compiled a set of web-based resources that contain resources for teaching and studying the events of 11 September 2001, their causes and the aftermath.

The premier site on 11September is the September 11 Digital Archive <<http://www.911digitalarchive.org/>>. It is a project of the American Social History Project at the City University of New York Graduate Center and the Center for History and New Media at George Mason University and funded by a grant from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. It contains first-hand accounts of the attacks and the aftermath in a collection of and archived emails and digital images growing out of these events. There are almost 2000 images and 8000 stories on the site. This site contains a link to The Sonic Memorial Project <<http://sonicmemorial.org/public/educators.html>> and a set of lesson plans devised by Robert W. Snyder a New York City historian who also tells of his story of being on the streets of Lower Manhattan when the towers collapsed: <<http://www.911digitalarchive.org/stories/details/72>>. The Sonic Memorial site contains interviews about the construction of the Towers, the Mohawk ironworkers, and various memories of the buildings.

Middlebury College's Center for Educational Technology has a 11September site with a course syllabus and multiple links to media stories <<http://manila.cet.middlebury.edu/911/>>

The Poynter Institute, a school for journalists, maintains a web page with multiple links including graphics of newspaper front pages from around the world < <http://www.poynter.org/Terrorism/default.htm>>. Also available are editorial cartoons and editorials in US and Canadian newspapers.

H-Net's H-Museum has a good web site with a variety of sources. Steven Mintz of the University of Houston provides a guide to Addressing Tragedy in the Classroom <<http://www2.h-net.msu.edu/teaching/journals/sept11/mintz/>>. A number of H-Net's groups discussed the events and their logs provide a variety of perspectives <<http://www2.h-net.msu.edu/teaching/journals/sept11/>>.

The Smithsonian Institution opened an exhibition 'September 11: Bearing Witness to History' on 11 September 2002. The online version contains images of various artifacts and video of American newscaster Peter Jennings's recollections of the event, which shows the confusion of the moment.

<<http://americanhistory.si.edu/september11/exhibition/highlights.asp>>

The 911 history site <<http://www.911history.net/Exhibitions.htm>> contains links to various online versions of museum exhibitions. Among these are various exhibitions from the Museum of the City of New York, The New York Historical Society, and others that cover the construction of the World Trade Center, materials on Arab-Americans in New York City, the notion of social infrastructure in the built environment and perhaps most poignantly the 'Missing: Last Seen at the World Trade Center on September 11, 2001' exhibition organized by Mesoamerica Foundation in Mexico, which collects the missing flyers posted in New York.

The archive <<http://september11.archive.org/>> is a collaboration between the Library of Congress, the Internet Archive and webArchivist.org. It brings together various web-based responses to September 11. Among those materials are the Pew Internet & American Life Project Reports on the impact of 11 September on the Internet:

<<http://www.pewinternet.org/reports/toc.asp?Report=69>>

The September 2002 issue of the *Journal of American History* is a special issue on 11 September. Individual subscribers and those in subscribing institutions that have made arrangements can view the full text on line at: <<http://www.historycoop.org/journals/jah/89.2/index.html>>. In addition the OAH web site offers a special teaching feature on Nick Cullather's article 'Damming Afghanistan: Modernization in a Buffer State' in that issue: <<http://www.indiana.edu/~jah/teaching/article.shtml>>

The official US government view on 11 September, its causes, and aftermath can be found on the FirstGov.gov portal:

<http://www.firstgov.gov/Topics/Usresponse.shtml>

Books

Syed Farid Alatas, National University of Singapore has a reading list on Islam & Contemporary Muslim Societies available at:

<<http://www.thecore.nus.edu.sg/civilizational/ucv2201/readings.html>>

Steven Mintz, University of Houston has an essential reading list on 11 September available at:

<http://www2.h-net.msu.edu/teaching/journals/sept11/mintz/readings.html>